

On the Border between Implication and Actuality: Children Inside and Outside of Picture Books

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Abstract

While the current hegemony of studies in literary education requires a commitment to the idea that individuals all respond to texts differently, a large body of research devoted to descriptions of the experiences of specific children with texts has the presumed purpose of increasing our understanding of literary response more generally. This essay explores the contradictions inherent in work committed to the uniqueness of individual response that nevertheless often seem to present its subjects as examples of more general truths about children's engagement with literature. After an analysis of the generalisations stated or implied in a number of reports of work with children and texts, I consider what it might or might not be safe to conclude from such work, and how the work might most become useful.

Introduction – the problem of response

According to David Lewis, there are two useful approaches to research in picture books for children: 'One route involves careful and patient listening to what children say as they read, the other an equally patient, careful description of individual books' (113). While my own work follows the second route, I find myself intrigued by the first one – and, also, somewhat troubled by it, for it raises questions that seem to me to deserve more consideration than they usually receive. What is, or ought to be, the place of children in the study of children's picture books? Which children, when, and why?

I suspect most critics of children's literature would agree that basing evaluations or understandings of books on generalisations about children and children's responses is a dangerous practice, either a thoughtless expression of conventional caricatures of childhood widespread in contemporary culture or an unquestioning acceptance of longstanding age-and-stage theories of development that have been

seriously undermined by newer psychological research in recent decades.¹ Furthermore, the current hegemony of literary studies means that most of us involved in literary education have an unquestioning commitment to the idea that individuals all respond to texts differently, that as Arizpe and Styles say, 'Although children's knowledge, understanding and values are culturally saturated, the extent to which this affects literary interpretation will always be mediated by each child's unique personality' (2003: 184) and that therefore, in Janet Evans' words, 'the texts are for us to interpret depending on *who* we are, *where* we are, *what* we need from the text, consciously or subconsciously at any particular moment' (2009: xiv). If we believe that to be the case, then logically, we have to acknowledge that all we can know, really, is how one child or a group of children we know actually responds. As a result, exploring those responses seems unlikely to teach us much of anything beyond an understanding of the taste, interests, and meaning-making strategies of these particular children, and little in the way of a more universally applicable understanding of childhood response to texts.

Nevertheless, Arizpe and Styles express their faith in the influence of personality on interpretation in the context of a study of 'how visual texts are read by children' (2003: 1) – the specific children in their study, but with what appears to be an unspoken assumption that the experiences of these unique individuals will offer meaningful information to those working with other children. And Evans implies a similar assumption when she says that she 'decided to work with a class of thirty-six 8 and 9-year old children' in order to try to find out 'how children would respond to a well-known picture book which presents an alternative view of a traditional fairy story' (1998: 101) – a specific group of children, once more, but with an aura of generalisation implied by the labelling of them not as *these* children but just as unspecified 'children.' Indeed, if some kind of generalisation or application to others in other situations weren't possible, there'd be little or no reason for anyone other than the parents and teachers of these specific groups of children to read about their experiences.

So, can we or should we generalise from them? How, if we are to avoid the kinds of generalisations most would surely agree are untenable? And why, if we wish to avoid those generalisations?

Despite the serious reservations these questions imply, I find myself again and again being personally fascinated by these descriptions of other adults' interactions with children and books. I have a sense that I

am indeed learning something of value from them and might learn even more, even if I'm not very clear about exactly what it is I'm learning or how I might gain further understanding from it. I also have a strong sense that if we hope to develop a useful understanding of books produced specifically for child reader/viewers, we cannot legitimately proceed without at least some consideration of that audience. As Pat Pinsent asserts, 'to look solely at the qualities of picture books valued by adults, without thinking of their primary audience, is to neglect an essential aspect of their creation' (Harding & Pinsent, 2008: 152). We cannot claim successfully to have understood a children's book we have read and looked at closely as informed adults if we have no ideas about its potential relationship to a surely quite different child audience. We cannot legitimately claim to understand children's books without having done any thinking about children.

But then how can or should we be thinking about them? My own practice as a literary critic with little knowledge of any child readers, other than my own three children when they were young, has been to focus on the reader/viewers texts imply – the repertoire of interpretive skills and information possessed by readers best equipped to understand them. I usually, therefore, follow the advice Mavis Reimer and I offer in our textbook for university students, *The Pleasures of Children's Literature*: 'By comparing your perception of a text's implied reader with children you know, you can determine what particular repertoire or special strategies of meaning-making might be required to understand and enjoy that particular text. You can decide whether the children you know are likely to be familiar with this repertoire and these strategies – and if they are not, how you might help them develop this knowledge' (2003: 20).

But what about children you don't know? How might what you know about the children you know be of interest or significance to others working with other children? In trying to answer these questions, I've explored existing descriptions of children responding to books published in the last few decades, and considered the ways in which they make spoken or unspoken claims to be offering useful knowledge about picture books, about children reading picture books, and about the interactions between books and children more generally. My purpose here is to consider the implications of these claims and the legitimacy of various justifications of this kind of work with children and books.

Published Studies of Children's Responses

The study of specific groups of children responding to books falls under the general category of qualitative research in the social sciences: close studies of small groups, as opposed to the quantitative analysis of information gleaned from large populations:

The detail in most qualitative research is both a blessing and a curse. On the positive side, it enables you to describe the phenomena of interest in great detail, in the original language of the research participants. On the negative side, when you have that kind of detail, it's hard to determine what the generalisable themes may be. In fact, many qualitative researchers don't even care about generalizing – they're content to generate rich descriptions of their phenomena. ('Qualitative Measures')

For many qualitative researchers, indeed, generalisability is not an issue: 'A small sample is selected precisely because the researcher wishes to understand the particular in depth, not to find out what is generally true of the many' (Merriam, 2002: 28). The research proceeds in the belief that the more completely detailed a descriptions of a specific group is, the more accurately it describes that one group, then the more likely it is that it allows for readers or users to determine how generalisable it might be; 'readers themselves determine the extent to which findings from a study can be applied to their context' (Merriam, 2002: 28-29). No claims are made other than the one that, since this one group has acted in this way, others may be better understood as being similar to or different from it. 'Indeed,' says Joseph Maxwell, 'the value of a qualitative study may depend on its lack of external generalizability in a statistical sense; it may provide an account of a setting or population that is illuminating as an extreme case or "ideal type"' (2002: 54).

Some of the research I've investigated takes a version of that stand. After describing his work with two young girls, for example, Victor Watson says, 'Ann and Sadie were very different readers ... and I do not think it possible to generalize about children reading post-modernist texts in a post-modernist age' (1996: 98). And after discussing how a group of Greek children created their own picture books, Vasiliki Labitsi is willing to conclude only that 'As well as developing narrative and art-making skills, they were able to negotiate and communicate messages, ideas and feelings that were important to them. Each book was a unique and powerful multimodal text that enabled its readers to have insights into the authentic interests, needs and preoccupations of these children (Harding

& Pinsent, 2008: 200). Labitsi leaves unconsidered the question of why what she describes here might matter to her readers – how what happened to ‘these children’ might be of value in thinking about the potential responses of other children. To insist on the individuality of child subjects is to undermine the validity and value of this sort of research in terms of its engendering of sharable, generalisable conclusions – other perhaps, than confirming what we already take for granted: that each child reads and responds differently.

Nevertheless, the descriptions of work with children and books I've read do make various sorts of claims to more generalisable knowledge. For instance, some researchers imply that the experiences with child readers they describe might be generalisable, but only in specific circumstances. After talking about how his own child developed some very specific interpretative skills, for instance, Michael Rosen says, ‘These kinds of awareness strike me as vital for turning children into readers. What is significant in that *in the right kind of circumstances*, children can teach themselves how to do this’ (1996:135; italics mine). He doesn't say what the right circumstances are, other than to imply, perhaps, that the ones he's described in this one case were clearly the right ones, and that success might therefore be guaranteed only for young white male middle-class offspring of a literate family with specific attitudes towards childhood freedom and of a very specific personality. In other words, Rosen offers the possibility of generalisability in a way that actually suggests just the opposite.

More often, however, generalising sneaks into this work in intriguingly slippery ways, as authors segue between individuals and generalisations about children. Sometimes, specific children transform into examples of generalised childhood – and then back again. For instance, Helen Bromley says that the specific children she worked with ‘had a working knowledge of artists such as Monet, Turner and Van Gogh’ (Watson & Styles, 1996: 106). A sentence later, these children slide into standing for all children: ‘This may surprise some teachers, but children today [note--the ‘these’ has disappeared] are visually sophisticated and don't find it difficult to recognize the styles of different artists and do find it interesting’ (1996: 106). By the time Bromley's essay concludes a few pages later, she says, ‘There is no doubt in my mind that young children can successfully identify intertextual links of both a written and illustrative nature’ (1996: 111). While the sentence might literally be understood to refer only to the specific children she has worked with, it does tend to suggest that what happened to them is generally possible for other

children also. The same thing happens in Janet Evans' statement, 'In an attempt to find out what children's thoughts were about reading and responding to picturebooks, I talked with some 11-year-old children with whom I had been working' (2009: xix). Either the first 'children' in this sentence refers to more than just this group or the sentence tautologically suggests that Evans talked with this group only in order to find out what this group thought.

A number of the essays I looked at expressed similarly slippery relationships between specific cases and generalised children. After having been told in an interview of the responses of specific children to his work, the author/illustrator Anthony Browne says, 'That's what pleases me so much to hear, *because children in a way are capable of so much more than most people think they are*' (Arizpe & Styles, 2003: 210; italics mine); the responses of just two children become evidence of the capabilities of all children. Morag Styles makes a similar leap from her experience of the children she has actually known to children generally: 'I have never known a child to look closely at a book he or she finds disagreeable. Children are their own censors' (1996: 42). The same thing may or may not be happening as Janet Evans discusses research by Carger: 'While working with some eight-year old bilingual children to investigate how the visual arts could support language and literacy learning, she found that children developed as art critics when they were given opportunities to talk about picturebooks ...' (Evans, 2009: 101). These children? Or, as the wording seems to imply, *all* children?

A similar lack of clarity about specific children and generalised ones seems to govern the research described by Kate Noble, work with children 'selected from two local schools' (Harding & Pinsent, 2008: 155) that leads her to reach a significantly wider conclusion: 'I found that young children have an acute awareness of the different communicative possibilities of word and image and that they use many different types of knowledge to make sense of picture books' (2008: 161). While this might mean merely that *these* children have that awareness, it seems to claim much more. So, similarly, does Arizpe and Styles' description of their work with children on Kitamura's *Lily Takes a Walk*: 'But how do young readers learn how picturebooks work? ... And how do they deal with the incoherent and the incomplete? We now explore some of these queries as interviewers and children follow Lily and Nicky's footsteps through the picturebook' (2003: 57).

In one more example, Brenda Parkes 'explores how emergent readers utilise the illustrations in picture books in their quest for meaning' by drawing on 'work from a three-year ethnographic study which documented, described, and analysed the experiences of two preschool children with their favourite picture story books,' but which focuses actually 'on how one child, Sarah, made use of illustrations to derive meaning from the text' (Evans, 1998: 44). Parkes then concludes, 'It seems evident that what the language user takes the sign to mean is a function of his or her purpose and background of experience at the time. The text and illustration form an open potential, part of a semiotic data pool, through which the child constantly generates new hypotheses and discovers new meanings' (1998: 50). The phrase 'the child' here might mean this specific child or a sort of universally generalised child; the phrasing certainly seems to be making a claim for the latter.

Sometimes, the claim is a little more explicit, and the experiences of specific children are presented as exemplary of already stated and assumed general truths. For instance, Morag Styles speaks of 'a possible link between the complexity of children's drawing and their interest in the pictures in picture books' (1996: 28), and then argues for this general theory about childhood by referring to 'a couple of drawings by my six-year-old nephew' (1996: 28). And a few pages later, she says, 'My next visit to school confirmed my hunches about children's ability to interpret and negotiate complex pictorial texts' (1996: 31).

In offering one specific experience as evidence of the truth of a larger generalisation, this sentence represents a pattern I have come to think of as 'the disappearing "the"'. Styles might well have said, and can be interpreted as meaning, 'My next visit to school confirmed my hunches about *the* children's ability to interpret and negotiate complex pictorial texts' – i.e., the particular children in question. But the absence of the 'the' implies a more widespread application of her conclusion. Styles and her collaborator Evelyn Arizpe similarly drop the word 'the' at many key points in their discussions of work with children: 'Our research shows that picturebooks encourage intellectual growth in children and we believe that they should be used more widely with older pupils as well as with younger children who are learning the rudiments of reading' (2003: 27); or, 'Browne is extremely funny and children laugh a lot as they read the book' (2003: 78). Sometimes, the 'the' gets dropped from one sentence to the next one: 'what we saw, even with the young children [i.e. specific ones they worked with] was what can only be described as intellectual excitement with the ideas raised by the book and aesthetic

pleasure in the images. It was as if *Zoo* offered an invitation that children [children generally?] felt compelled to take up' (2003: 80). Or, 'In this chapter we will analyse some of the comments children made about reading visual texts in an attempt to understand the thought processes behind these skills. ... finally, we shall try to pull all these observations together in order to understand how children make sense of their own meaning-making processes' (2003: 191). Arizpe on her own avoids a 'the' when she says of another research project, 'these extracts from the girls' discussion reveal the potential for children's sharing and building on each others' interpretations of visual images in picturebooks' (2003: 144).

Arizpe and Styles are not alone in disappearing the word 'the'. Their colleague Kate Rabey says, 'By looking at the drawings of my reception class and analysing their discussions during our study of *Zoo*, I have found that children can see the most incredible things beyond what they might be assumed to know' (quoted in Arizpe and Styles, 2003: 222). Carol Fox describes how some of the five children she studied quoted from books they knew in their own stories, then concludes, 'I believe the implication is that children [generally, it appears] hear their favourite stories as metaphors for their own concerns, their own emotions, their own lives' (1993: 12). Margaret Meek similarly suggests in her foreword to Fox's book that 'this book makes clear that children [without a 'the,' so presumably all children?] use storying to sort out their own knowledge and ideas' (viii). A 'the' is also absent from Sylvia Pantaleo's claim in an essay describing specific children's responses to Lauren Child's *Who's Afraid of the Big Bad Book* that her work 'explores children's responses to and interpretations of some of the metafictional devices in this postmodern picturebook' (Evans, 2009: 46).

In his book *Storytime*, Lawrence Sipe makes it clear that he understands the problem I've been outlining: 'While it is true that qualitative interpretive research attempts to present description that is complete and nuanced enough for the readers of the research to make their own connections with other situations and contexts, the true challenge is to go beyond the "epistemology of the particular" (Stake, 240) into a generalizability that is wary of the dangers of master narratives of any behavior, including children's literary and visual meaning-making' (2008: 35). Sipe claims to have dealt with the problem by generalising about 'a narrower band of age groups' and representing in his group of participants 'diversity among several dimensions, including race, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status' (2008:35); but he doesn't describe

the principles or the methodology that led him to choose these representatives, or on what basis he feels it safe to assume that they do represent a larger population of American children, or perhaps even, all children. Nevertheless, he claims to have 'built a grounded theory of young children's literary understanding based on this work (2008: 1) – not just 'the young children' or 'these young children,' but, it seems, children generally.

Sometimes, these researchers justify the generalised conclusions they derive from their specific interaction with particular children by referring to a context of their previous experience with many other children that confirms similar results. Victor Watson is thus able to assert that the qualities of the specific children's conversations he's describing are 'all characteristic of a particular kind of classroom talk' (1996:88) he's often experienced, and to claim that 'I learned from working with a number of children over several years ... that labelling quickly develops into interpretation' (1996: 147). But as Karl Popper once suggested of a similar comment by the psychologist Alfred Adler, 'his previous observations may not have been much sounder than this new one ... each in its turn had been interpreted in the light of "previous experience," and at the same time counted as additional confirmation. What, I asked myself, did it confirm? No more than that a case could be interpreted in the light of a theory' (46).

It is more common, however, for researchers to justify their generalisations not in terms of their own previous experience of children, but in terms of the experience – or even just the generalising theory – of others. The responses of the specific children they work with are placed in the context of, and assumed to be representative of, generalisations already current in scholarship. Thus, Helen Bromley accounts for one child's interesting responses by saying, 'All the interactions between Momahl, the children and the picture book seem to me to be examples of scaffolded learning' (Watson & Styles, 1996: 140) – i.e., of learning theories originated by Vygotsky. After describing one child's responses, Arizpe and Styles say, 'This shows how Piaget's "pre-operational child" is dealing with the environment at a perceptual level and acting upon it' (2003: 33), and in another instance, 'The readers were determined to make sense of the story, to try and explain why the things appeared in the illustrations, to fit it into a coherent whole ... This coincides with Gardner's description of the child's early development with respect to story' (2003: 102-103). Peggy Rice makes reference to two experts in

generalising the behaviour of the children in the study of reading multicultural literature she describes:

... the children were unable to relate to a character's actions and tended to 'put down' the character, mainly due to their perception that a character lacked intelligence or education. The boys were more inclined to make this type of put down, and the girls were more inclined to make them in mixed-sex discussions rather than the single sex discussions. Tannen (1990) has noted that males tend to be judgmental of others. Bleich (1988) characterizes males' inability to react positively to or identify with characters as a "male" stance of detachment. (2005: 350)

After referring to a series of psychological theorists' work on language learning, Carol Fox announces her intention to 'return to the children's story material, and to see how these ideas map onto what is under scrutiny here' (1993: 29). She concludes that these 'theoretical issues . . . provide some explanation for the linguistic operations the children [in her study] were involved in' (1993: 35).

What interests me about all these arguments is the circularity they establish. The children under investigation become evidence for the theory, which makes the theory seem more valid, which then intensifies its forcefulness as an explanation for the children's behaviour. As result, children as a whole come to seem more like each other, more able to accommodate and accord with generalisations about childhood behaviour. And meanwhile, I have a sense that the possibility of other explanations is not being considered. As happens often in research in all fields, the temptation to confirm pre-existing patterns and explanations sometimes leaves paths to newer kinds of understanding unexplored.

Thus, for instance, Carol Fox tells us that she chose to include only five of the ten children she considered for her study 'because for a variety of reasons the other children did not find storytelling a very natural activity' (1995: 18); but she then tends to forget the existence of the eliminated five when she generalises from the five who did enjoy the activity about the apparently natural storytelling abilities of children generally. A more persuasive project might have included the less interested ones and made more careful generalisations as a result.

Another example is Kathy Coulthard's description of their work with Eylem, a second-generation Cypriot whose response to her questions about a picture book 'suggests to me that Eylem understands reading as

a process of retrieval, one in which the meaning is fixed in words with little or no space for interpretation' – an understanding 'at odds with' her own commitment to more scope for individual response (Arizpe & Styles, 2003: 186). Coulthard offers various reasons for Eylem's inability to adopt her view, including his membership in an immigrant 'community with a long history of low reading attainment', his lack of familiarity with the kinds of questions she's asking and the attitude towards pictures they imply, and his involvement in a reading programme that focuses on phonics and 'is not helping him to become literate in the fullest sense' (2003: 188). But she never considers the possibility that Eylem might simply not like her approach or find it meaningful or useful – that he is an individual person with an idea about what matters different from her own, does what works best for him, and has no particular interest in what matters so much to her, or in becoming more like she is and less like the other members of that 'community with a long history of low reading attainment.' Her commitment to her own way of doing things as the better one leads her to be critical of an individual's response different from her own, and also, appears to blind her to ways in which that different response might be open to interpretations other than those supported in, argued for in, and championed by the existing research.

In any case, and despite their cleavage to the idea that we are all unique individuals with unique responses, some of the researchers I explored do generalise about children's interactions with books, sometimes, even, without any attempt to justify them. In the process of arguing that another researcher's work with children reveals their access to sophisticated humour, for instance, Barbara Jordan expresses the conviction that 'Children are naturally highly observant and do not miss the humorous details that Anthony Browne has embedded in his pictures' (Watson & Styles 1996:53-4), without presenting any evidence or argument or even authority for it. It is simply taken for granted.

Optimism and Propaganda

So why, then, all the generalisations? The answer, I think, emerges from a consideration of two significant aspects of all this work – aspects that I actually can't help but approve of. First, it is optimistic. Second, it is propagandistic.

The optimism emerges from a distinguishing quality of just about all the generalisations I found in this work. Unlike the vast majority of the generalisations about children that characterise discourse about childhood in cultures around the world now and in the past few centuries,

these ones emphasise capability rather than deficiency. Most often, generalisations about children focus on what they can't do rather than on what they can. In *Pleasures of Children's Literature*, Mavis Reimer and I list a number of these:

Children have limited understanding and short attention spans. ... Children are innocent by nature, blissfully naive. ... they aren't interested in matters outside their own immediate experience. They dislike stories about people unlike themselves living in places unlike their own. ... they have a basic dislike for thinking and learning, for experiencing anything different from what they know and like already. (2003: 86-87)

Any of us could easily find examples expressive of ideas like these in just about any conversation most people have about children and books – even many specialists in childhood or education. I heard them constantly in my three decades of teaching prospective teachers in children's literature classes. Because limiting ideas like these are so widespread, the researchers I'm exploring here clearly have a sense that the results they're describing go against most people's ideas about what children are capable of or ought to experience in the way of literature and literary education – and so, I suspect, they tend to be overly confident about how easily what they have done with a few children might represent the potential of all children everywhere. They tend, then, to jump past the obvious truth that their research shows that at least some children are more capable than the usual generalisations suggest, to the illogical and unlikely implication that all children are. It's telling that Arizpe and Styles, for instance, are so grudging in their acknowledgement that 'it was rare for the picturebooks to fail to make an impact on the children in our study, but in the odd individual (in one case a hyperactive child with a short attention span), little or no engagement was possible and so the activity was fairly worthless' (2003: 44). They hold on stubbornly, optimistically, and, I must say, endearingly, to their idea that children generally are capable and that the one with a low attention span is the exception rather than the norm most people assume it is.

And that happens because of the propaganda aspects of this work. It is not merely or purely the scientifically objective research it represents itself as. It is also and clearly work that emerges from a conviction that children deserve more respect than they usually get and that most teachers, parents, and other adults could do more and better. The specific work described is not just a series of case studies considered in

the light of what they reveal, then. They are also being presented as good examples of what can be done and might be done and *should* be done.

This is important work. Many children can often do more than most people suspect, and benefit from having access to adults who believe they can do more and help them to do it. I suspect Lawrence Sipe and Caroline McGuire are quite right in saying in their study about the implications of picture book endpapers that, 'If teachers attend to the meaning of endpapers, children will too' (Evans, 2009: 78), even though I'm not convinced of the universal truth of their assertion that as a result, 'their literary and visual aesthetic experience will be enhanced.' (Evans, 2009: 78). Just as some children don't like asparagus, some otherwise sane and happy children surely would surely simply rather not care about endpapers, and never will.

In my experience such work would be particularly beneficial in North America, where the currently most powerful ideology in literary education remains the idea that any form of instruction by a teacher is an intrusive encroachment on a child's right to and development of an individual response, and where even the possibility that more than one child might be asked to read and discuss the same text at the same time is viewed as repressive, a violation of the children's right to read only what each of them wants to read and then only when they want to. In the light of the widespread cleavage to such ideas in North American classrooms, I can understand why the researchers I'm considering here might want to work hard to suggest that their faith in children's ability to engage in, enjoy, and gain from critical discussion and analysis with specific pedagogical goals is indeed justified.

On the other hand, I worry about the ways in which the propaganda dilutes the scientific objectivity of the conclusions being reached. Claiming too much for their work in terms of its application elsewhere might well be undermining the very ideals these writers rightly want to propagandise for.

Legitimate conclusions from these studies

This dichotomy brings me back to my original question: what might legitimately be learned in the way of shareable knowledge from work with a specific child or group of children? If the kinds of generalisations I've been outlining are too confident and go too far, what might be legitimate kinds of conclusions to draw from this sort of work?

Firstly, researchers might focus more explicitly than they often do on ways in which their work can *challenge* generalising and undermine ideas others take for granted. Rice offers an example of this when she says her study shows that 'it is important not to assume that children will identify with the universal experiences portrayed by characters in multicultural stories with universal themes. In this study, the students' "identity kits" limited their interpretations of these multicultural stories with universal themes to the point that aesthetic restriction occurred and the children did not view these realistic fiction short stories as realistic.' (2005: 357).

Secondly, while the fact that some children did accomplish something doesn't prove that all children can accomplish it, it *is* evidence that not all children's *can't* accomplish it. It does reveal that negative generalisations about things such as low attentions spans and inability to think abstractly or make subtle ethical judgements are not universally true. Carol Fox presents an argument of this sort when she asserts, 'I want to challenge Piaget's view [that young children are egocentric and incapable of seeing things as someone else might] by showing that the children in my study were sometimes able to vary point of view in their narratives' (1993: 121). This sort of challenge is important in itself. As long as contemporary hegemonic discourse about childhood remains so firmly intertwined with ideas of incapacity, we need constantly to remind ourselves and each other that children might not be merely and always incapable. Assumptions about children's lack of ability are so powerful that even researchers who are committed to proving greater capability often do so in terms of expressing their own surprise at what can be accomplished. For instance, Kate Noble says, 'By looking at, talking about and drawing what they saw and understood in these picture books, the four and five year olds in my class appeared to discover much more than I would have expected' (Harding & Pinsent, 2008: 153). In introducing Bromley's discussion of her work with children, Arizpe and Styles say, 'Although she has always held strong views on the capacities of young children to read pictorial texts with insight and intelligence, even Helen Bromley was surprised at the intertextual understandings of this class of six-year-olds' (2003: 101). And throughout *Storytime*, Sipe refers to the children's comments on the books they interact with as 'marvellous', as something 'we can only marvel at', as 'unbelievably sophisticated', and as enabling 'a sense of wonder' at their sophistication (2008: 10; 97; 165; 2).

This sort of wonder and surprise also reveals some unnecessary and counterproductive modesty at work: it seems obvious to me that these projects succeeded because the adults involved in them had the belief that they could succeed and the knowledge and experience to figure out how to make them succeed. One of the negative side-effects of insisting that the result of these experiments is proof that children are generally more capable than most people think, is that such a claim underemphasises not just the individuality and talent of these individual children but also the individuality and talent of these individual adult teachers and researchers. In fact, this work does, quite usefully and shareably, stand as evidence for the nature and value of sound, productive pedagogical practices – examples of what teachers with significant goals together with ideas about how to meet these can accomplish.

It is unfortunate, then, that these researchers are often so determined to make their point about how clever children can be that they seriously underplay how clever they are themselves. While Sipe and McGuire acknowledge that their work demonstrates 'the interest and interpretive sophistication even young children can demonstrate given teachers' support' (Evans 2009:76), most throw the spotlight on the children and underplay the significance of their own involvement. Arizpe and Style do wonder if, 'Rather than finding out what they already knew about picturebooks, were we actively teaching them how to look?' (2003: 10). They eventually acknowledge that 'Our interaction with children may have shaped their responses in ways which were not planned' (2003: 243). But they also want to assert that the exposure to sophisticated books and the children's inherent potential were more important than their own convictions and actions: 'The children in our study found reading picturebooks an intellectual activity partly because we did. We do, however, believe that most of the children would have become engaged with the texts had we not been present' (2003: 246). More justifiable pride in their own fine work might have led them to generalise less about children and focus more on the specific beliefs, skills, and strategies they used and might recommend that others try with other children – as, for instance, Sipe does in a chapter that analyses how the teachers the children in his study worked by encouraging their students' sophisticated responses.

More awareness of adult influence in these sorts of encounters might also lead researchers in this field to become more aware of something Sipe *doesn't* consider in that chapter: how they work, consciously or

more often, unconsciously, to have children agree with their own reading methodologies and their own interpretations. Bromley says of her work with one child, 'I was so impressed with Momahl's reaction to the book, that I praised her profusely, whilst the rest of the class sat on the carpet rather bemused by my obvious excitement' (Watson & Styles, 1996: 139) – but she doesn't go on to consider the possibly negative implications of how her excitement acted as a propagandistic influence for specific ideas and interpretations on the children around her. Janet Evans similarly says that 'I was delighted that the children, working together and drawing on their own personal knowledge base, noted the symbolism used by Botero [the artists she studied with them]' (2009: 109-110), but similarly does not explore the implications of her pleasure in the children achieving what she wished and understanding the paintings as she herself did. Furthermore, as Mazzei and Jackson argue, 'Letting readers 'hear' participant voices and presenting their "exact words" as if they were transparent is a move that fails to consider how as researchers we are always already shaping those "exact words" through the unequal power relationships present and by our own exploitative research agendas and guidelines. ... How might voices be distorted and fictionalized in the process of reinscription?' (2) A stronger commitment to exploring all the possible ways in which one's own presence and values might have affected the work could go a long way toward making this sort of research a richer resource for furthering our understanding of how adults pass on their ideologies to children. Additionally, if we are truly committed to the ideal of individuals responding differently, it would also make it a valuable indicator of how we might become conscious of and get past the unconscious ways in which we as adults limit the range of possible acts, practices and interpretations even in the faith that we are encouraging individual response.

A fuller commitment to awareness of adult involvement might also increase our understanding of how social arrangements and practices might play their part in shaping children. The discovery that differing groups of children of a similar age in differing places or economic circumstances or cultural contexts have similar responses might be considered not just as evidence of universal childhood capabilities, but also in the light of how widespread assumptions about children and widespread pedagogical goals and strategies might be working to regularise childhood experience, thus resulting in children being more like each other than they might otherwise have been.

It's intriguing for instance, how many of these researchers use the work of Anthony Browne, particularly the two books *Tunnel* (1989) and *Zoo* (1992), how much they love these books themselves, and how almost all the children they work with come to love them also – thus giving more credence to the generalisation that all children are capable of responding positively to this sophisticated sort of picture book.² But what if the children had all learned to admire a different book from adults who loved it – one called, say, *Everyone Unlike Me Is Ugly and Stupid*, or perhaps *Benny Bunny Stops Wasting Precious Time on Reading Books and Ends Up Rich and Famous*. Would that equally be evidence of the children's sophistication, or just of their malleable willingness to conform to the pre-existing assumptions of powerful adults?

In terms of exploring pressures to conform, I'm also intrigued by Evelyn Arizpe's conclusion that the conversations between girls from different cultural minorities which she reports in her study represent a potential 'for approaching and understanding the differences in personal experiences, leading the way to sharing values as future citizens of the same country' (2003: 144). Does this ambiguously worded phrase mean that the girls communicate their different values and thus share them with each other, or rather that their conversations are moving them towards a sharing of the same values as each other – as, for instance, an unspoken agreement with the mainstream democratic idea that such discussions are helpful and valuable? Are the girls actually becoming less different, and if so, is that necessarily a welcome development? A fuller exploration of the ideological forces at work here could be highly instructive.

As well as paying more attention to their own role and to the role of ideology in the processes they describe, it might also be possible that researchers on children's responses to literature might achieve more persuasive generalisations by making more use of practices conventional in other areas of social-science research: more carefully controlled processes of sampling and randomisation, more use of techniques such as control groups and double-blind trials – techniques that might imply more valid generalisations. I suspect, however, that the introduction of these sorts of quantitative practices might well fragment and distort the very processes the researchers are hoping to understand. The problem here is not that the work I'm describing is qualitative rather than quantitative; it is that the qualitative work needs to be less dependent on unspoken and taken-for-granted assumptions about both children and literature, and more attentive to the wide range of

implications of the encounters between children and books that it so intriguingly and so usefully records.

Conclusion

I began to think about investigating this topic at a graduate students' conference in Canada, where I listened to a paper in which a doctoral student described her research sharing books with a specific group of children but offered no explanation of how she understood the work to be a contribution to our overall knowledge of books and children. I assumed, though, that she did have a rationale for her project, a goal of some sort of shareable understanding she had neglected to mention, so in the question period after her paper, I asked her what it was. If she was as committed to the idea that individuals respond individually as she claimed, how might what these children did apply to situations involving other children? To my surprise, she had no answer, other than to say that it was an interesting question and that she'd have to think about it more. Worse, an hour or two later, another young woman rushed up to me and said, 'Professor Nodelman, you've ruined my thesis!' She'd heard me ask my question earlier, she too had a project reporting on work with specific children, and she too had just realised that she had no idea whatsoever about what the purpose or goal of her work might be, or what it could teach others about other children. She'd simply been taking it for granted that it had to have some sort of value or other, and now she felt crushed.

I did my best to reassure her that her two years of work was not a waste, by suggesting that she could consider some of the possible implications of her work which I've outlined here. I hope it helped. But I found myself worrying that the validity of work describing specific interactions with children and books was being so taken for granted that neither of the advisors of these young scholars had asked them to think about what their work was for or what it might accomplish. The most productive research into children's reading will take the least for granted – not the usefulness or purpose or goal of the work, not the value of the researchers' own values or of the books they admire, not the implications of specific environments and populations, not the generalisability of their results. Researchers need to be especially aware of what might be counterproductive in what they cherish and believe in, the possible negative implications of their own positive behaviour. A firm commitment to this kind of self-critical thinking has the best chance of producing knowledge that is, if not generalisable, nevertheless usefully shareable.

Notes

1. For a survey of these developments, see *The Pleasures of Children's Literature*, the textbook by me and Mavis Reimer, 91-95.
2. As an anonymous reviewer of this essay pointed out, 'One factor may be that Browne regularly gives fee-free permission for the reproduction of his illustrations in academic publications.'

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